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Teaching for Sustainable Futures: Empowering Educators for Holistic Innovation and Global Citizenship

ABSTRACT

The Narratives of Community Garden Beneficiaries of Gawad Kalinga ERH Village: A Social Behavioral Change Evaluation

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Abstract:

This study assesses the social and behavioral changes of Project Kauswagan: Pagtanom sang Mauswag nga Bwas-Damlag, a youth-led community development initiative under the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand. The class project aimed to address the lack of sustainable livelihood and food security in the ERH Gawad Kalinga Village, Brgy. Sum-ag, Bacolod City, through the establishment of a community garden that promotes agricultural skills, sustainability, and self-sufficiency—aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals SDG 2: Zero Hunger and SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities. The assessment covered the implementation period from May 2024 to March 2025. Data were collected through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with key community leaders and were analyzed thematically using the Colaizzi method. The results revealed six major themes: (1) empowerment through leadership and responsibility, (2) formation of community habits and routines, (3) shift in attitudes toward sharing and collaboration, (4) motivation and ownership in garden maintenance, (5) positive impact on food security and community welfare, and (6) encouragement of sustainable practices and financial independence. These themes highlight how the project empowered individuals—particularly women—to strengthen collaboration and enhance food accessibility through sustainable livelihood practices. Overall, Project Kauswagan served as a catalyst for behavioral transformation and community resilience. It strengthened local leadership, promoted sustainability, and advanced progress toward the SDGs by empowering marginalized groups to achieve food security and self-sufficiency.

Keywords: Community development; garden; agriculture; leadership; service learning

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